

IMPROVEMENT OF STUDENTS' LISTENING COMPETENCY IN MUSIC PEDAGOGICAL ACTIVITY AS A PEDAGOGICAL PROBLEM

Avlakulov Dilovor Hayitboboyevich

Teacher of the "Preschool education" department of the Denov Entrepreneurship and
Pedagogical Institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10776088>

Abstract. *This article describes the discussion of the concepts of pedagogical problems of improving students' listening competence in musical education and music pedagogical activities.*

Key words: *music, education, pedagogy, knowledge, skill, personality, professional, competence, culture.*

Introduction. The process of musical pedagogic education shows that it is necessary to analyze the improvement of the listening competence of students of undergraduate music education as an important pedagogical problem. Improving listening competence is one of the important components of musical pedagogical education and requires defining the essence of the concepts of competence, musical pedagogical competence, listening competence, improving listening competence.

Competence and competence have been widely studied by Uzbek scientists. However, the study of scientific literature on competence showed that there is no single point of view on the definition of these categories and their components.

The encyclopedic dictionary gives the following definition of competence. Competition (Latin *competo* - I achieve; I obey, I approach, I am able):

- 1) scope of powers granted to a specific body or official by law, charter or other document;
- 2) means knowledge, skill, qualification, experience in a certain field.

According to the definitions of S. Whiddett and S. Halliford, "based on behavior within the organization", "Competition is the behavior shown by an individual during the effective performance of tasks within a certain organization" [2].

"Competence is the main characteristic of a person that allows him to perform a job, fulfill a social role, or act at the highest level in a certain situation."

Main part. Jane Weitman states that behavior is based on the competencies required to achieve a desired outcome. "Competence is something you can demonstrate. Competency shows how to identify, assess, develop, achieve results, etc. Some desirable characteristics or competencies are easy to identify, measure, and develop[2]. However, many of them find it difficult. But it is self-evident that the work of some people is more effective than the work of others even in these problem areas. "Competition deals with the analysis of the reasons why human activity is more effective and enumerates all the organizing factors."

The word "competence" is used in many contexts and with different meanings. Based on research, competence is divided into three categories or types[6]:

- organizational competence is a unique factor for being competitive;
- official competence - this is the qualities and skills that a person must demonstrate in order to achieve efficiency in a position, role, task;

- personal competence - personal aspects that mean skills, achievements and results of human life [6].

Therefore, competence is an integral whole of planned knowledge, abilities, skills and personal qualities acquired during life under the influence of external and internal factors.

There are many types of competencies, one of which is educational and cognitive. Education and cognitive competence - a set of skills and abilities of cognitive activity; master the mechanisms of setting goals, planning, analyzing, reasoning, self-assessing the success of one's activities; know ways of acting in non-standard situations, heuristic methods of solving problems; to have the skills to understand, know, listen and measure musical works, to use statistical and other methods of knowledge evaluation.

The focus of modern higher education on training the future qualified teacher sets the task of defining the concept of undergraduate competencies more clearly. Competence in the process of professional training is the integrated integrity of planned knowledge, skills, competences, professional and personal qualities acquired by bachelors in the educational process in accordance with the normative requirements of the specialty.

There are basic and special competitions. The main competencies of students of higher pedagogical organizations that reflect the specific characteristics of the future music teacher's professional-pedagogical activity include professional, psychological-pedagogical, information and general culture. Basic competencies are necessary for the implementation of the main types of professional activity of a specialist, which are strictly connected with a certain profession or group of professions. These competencies are macroprofessional and constitute an invariable part of professional competencies. Basic competencies provide universal training for a future specialist. They are multi-functional, supra-subject, multi-dimensional and form an invariable part of professional competences[1].

Researchers offer different classifications of the main competencies that determine the modern quality of educational content. The basis for determining the main powers is the social order, which should reflect not only the interests of the state and society, but also the individual. Special powers are related to the implementation of a certain type of professional activity and solving its specific tasks. Special competitions are a variable part of professional competitions.

The last decade is characterized by the integration of various pedagogical approaches to the process of improving basic competencies, which is developing in accordance with the concept of humanization of education: it includes competency-based approaches that ensure the orientation of music education to the improvement of basic competencies. They are: self-determination; self-realization of effective activities in music education; person-oriented approach; cultural approach; contextual approach; problematic approach; systematic approach; axiological approach[3].

Any competition is considered as a complex formation. According to local scientists N.Muslimov, O.Koysinov, the content of any competence includes the following components:

- a) knowing the content of competence (cognitive aspect);
- b) willingness to demonstrate competence (motivational aspect);
- c) content of competence and attitude to the object of its application (value-semantic aspect);
- d) experience of demonstrating competence in various standard and non-standard situations (behavioral aspect).

Basic, musical-professional and special competences, knowledge and experience necessary for effective activity in a certain field of science existence is called competence.

According to competence, a number of researchers (N.A.Goncharova, A.A.Derkach, I.A.Zimnyaya, V.V.Kraevskii, N.V.Kuzmina, etc.) understand the integrative quality of a person, which is formed during the educational process and reflects the real acquisition of knowledge, skills, and abilities, and put them into practice. It is manifested in the ability and readiness to perform activities. Thus, competence is considered as the goal of improving students' listening competence in the process of musical pedagogical education and as an educational result [2].

In the field of pedagogy, competence is interpreted as a measure of the conformity of the knowledge, skills and professional qualifications of persons with a certain social status, acquired personal experience to the level of real complexity of the tasks they perform and the problems they solve. Unlike the term "competence", in addition to the purely professional knowledge and skills that characterize the competence, it includes such qualities as initiative, cooperation, ability to work in a group, communication skills, learning, evaluation, thinking ability.

Many foreign researchers (E.F.Zeer, E.A.Klimov, A.K.Markova, A.S.Petelin, L.G.Semushina, N.N.Tulkiboeva, A.I.Shcherbakov, etc.) study competence within the framework of professional-pedagogical activity and define it as a sum of theoretical knowledge, a cumulative phenomenon. As a result of in-depth analysis of practical skills and professional qualities of a future music teacher, they determine the following components of competence[2]:

- special knowledge in pedagogical sciences (pedagogy, professional specialization, etc.);
- communication skills and person-oriented interaction with students and educational participants;
- recognizing the value of another person, encouraging creative activity, initiative, having diagnostic tools, etc.;
- personal qualities of professional importance.

However, it should be noted that some CIS researchers (S.G.Vershlovsky, E.N.Gusinsky, N.V.Solovyova, Yu.N.Turchaninova) do not associate competence with certain knowledge and skills[2; 1; 4]. They believe that with the development of science, culture, restructuring of social consciousness, changes in the content and methods of teaching, knowledge, skills and abilities become obsolete, that is, people's needs, goals, norms, situations, cultural the patterns change and at the same time the qualification requirements do not change. Competence is manifested as a unity of professional and personal components of pedagogical activity, but the focus is on the priority of personal qualities, including independence, discipline, communication, the desire for self-development, the ability to adapt to certain working conditions. taste

The process of reforming the higher education system shows that its need for qualified pedagogical personnel is growing significantly. At the same time, many researchers emphasize that professional competence can be improved only in a working teacher. Solving this contradiction determines the need to study the process of improving professional competence as a set of theoretical knowledge, practical experience, and personal qualities already in the process of training future music teachers.

The professional competence of the future music teachers is the theoretical unity of the bachelor who is considered as a student of the bachelor's course of music education, his practical and psychological preparation for the implementation of professional activities, his readiness and ability to act in accordance with work requirements, professional problems, problems in a

methodical manner. is considered as a dynamic integral professional and personal characteristic that expresses organized and independent decision-making and evaluation of the results of one's activities.

In the process of research, considering their views on the concept of "professional competence", we found that competences can be included in all specialties of the pedagogical profile. At the same time, the qualification of a music teacher is unique. This uniqueness depends on the characteristics of music as an art form and a special discipline.

The current system of training a future music teacher has developed under the influence of conservative processes, where the purpose of training is the highly specialized training of a specialist for the activities of a teacher, musician, concertmaster in special musical educational institutions. The purpose of music pedagogy education is to prepare a future music teacher of a general education school, for which the presence of pedagogical skills and the subordination of musicality, artistry, creativity, equipment, conducting techniques and other similar special skills to the future music is the basis for improving the teacher's professional skills.

Professional training of a young music teacher E.B.Abdullin, Y.B.Aliev, O.A. Apraksina, L.G.Archajnikova, A.C.Bazikov, D.B.Kabalevsky is reflected in the studies and works [2; 3; 7].

With a fundamental study of the activities of the future music teacher, music education undergraduate students are related to the study of various special subjects, such as music-theoretical, related to the training of future music teachers. There are a number of justifications, each of which is important in relation to its own teaching methodology. These are: learning to play an instrument, singing solo, and acquiring knowledge of musical literacy. But the direction of all methods should be general - it is necessary to prepare for the implementation of multifaceted activities in a general secondary school.

The professional competencies of the future music teacher, teacher of his artistic and aesthetic cycle, culture and art worker are mainly a complex of musical and didactic knowledge and skills, the ability to perform actions optimally, business and personal qualities of music specialists. integral characteristics, the ability to effectively solve the problems of professional activity, integrated professional and personal characteristics, readiness and ability to perform professional and pedagogical functions in new conditions in accordance with the service status, to study the characteristics of the dialectical unity of professional and personal characteristics that allow successful implementation of professional and pedagogical activities we tried[1; 4; 5].

The professional qualification of the future music teacher understands the characteristics of the students of the bachelor's course of music education, in which the leading quality is practical for the implementation of professional musical pedagogical activities based on the integration of pedagogical and special abilities, learned knowledge, and formed skills. prepares.

Under the conditions of music education, the foundations of professional competence of undergraduate students are improved in the process of studying general professional and special subjects. The improvement of the training of future music teacher specialists depends not only on the correct direction of students during the teaching process in special classes, but also on the general methodological equipment and practical tools acquired in all the diversity of the studied subjects. At the same time, the narrow subject orientation of general pedagogic and special subjects contradicts both the complex nature of this educational process and the complex nature of the activity of a future music teacher in general, which significantly complicates the training of a

specialist, which is pedagogical in bachelors. it is clearly manifested in the practice process, and then in the practical independent activity in the general secondary school.

A student of a bachelor's degree in music education is a future music teacher who first of all improves his professional training, improves the competence of listening to music, and multifaceted and deep knowledge of various musical-theoretical disciplines. provides the necessity of having knowledge. It is not easy to do this in the current higher education educational system, therefore, one of the possible ways to get out of the current situation is to improve the teaching methodology of science education subjects, taking into account the existing interdisciplinary relations, and to prepare students for a new integrity. - leads to mastering of holistic knowledge.

Based on research on the professional competence of a music teacher, by musical competence we understand the unity of professional and personal components based on deep knowledge and skills in the field of musical pedagogical activities and the ability to apply them in practical activities.

Improving the professional qualification of music listeners of undergraduate students of music education is more effective in the conditions of creative self-awareness of the student. Philosophical, sociological and psychological levels are distinguished in the analysis of scientific literature on the problem of self-realization of a person. At the philosophical level, the essence of a person, his main forces, the essence of the process of self-realization and its forms, the role of cultural values in the process of self-realization, which determine the specific characteristics of the mentality of a certain nation, Cultural and historical types of self-awareness are reflected [5].

In the process of mastering the musical pedagogical components of the students, questions about the ways and means of self-realization of the individual in certain socio-cultural conditions are solved. At the level of pedagogical competence, personal qualities and external conditions are analyzed, people are encouraged to express themselves effectively, motivational bases of self-awareness are studied.

Music pedagogy analysis of research and study of actual pedagogical practice shows that with a clear understanding of the need for scientific development of the concept of "self-awareness", "self-development", "improving the ability to listen to music" , the understanding of the essence of this phenomenon is carried out in the context of studying concepts close to its importance: self-determination, self-organization, self-management, self-realization, self-expression. Thus, the phenomenon of self-awareness appears as one of the functional blocks of a person's self-development. He studies the social functions of the future music teacher, his role in the process of socialization of young people, issues related to personality improvement, creativity, and self-awareness [7].

The interpretation of this concept is chosen depending on how the problem of self-awareness is included in the scope of the researcher's scientific interests. Self-awareness, self-expression, self-affirmation, independence, listening, listening comprehension, listening thinking, the ability to achieve one's goals, to protect one's rights in appropriate situations , self-awareness is expressed in a system of various relationships in which personality is included.

Self-awareness of students is the implementation of a system of relationships in the process of purposefully formed pedagogical guidance and educational influences that make up the content of creative self-awareness. Realization of these relations determines the essence of the phenomenon of creative self-realization.

Music education considers the creative self-awareness of undergraduate students as a symbol of their purposefully formed diverse relationships, creative abilities, personal self-expression to others in interactions with the world, people.

In the process of music pedagogy education, the improvement of students' listening ability takes place in the process of studying the educational subjects of the humanitarian cycle, their distinctive feature is "a special way of teaching to improve the experience of realizing emotional-volitional and emotional-value relations. is a complaint.

In accordance with the nature of the humanities, therefore, the subject itself cannot be assimilated only at the level of values, since its true assimilation involves the determination of meaning and relations through internal polemics, feelings, experience, and sub- objects means communication with the future music teacher, feeling oneself in the product of one's creativity. Research shows that the characteristics of the content of humanities determine the specific characteristics of the music teacher's knowledge in the process of professional personal formation. These are:

- effective knowledge of the humanitarian topic in the context of communication. It is a dialogue between the teacher and the student, the author of the musical work and the listener, the work of art itself and the translator. Dialogicity is manifested in the relationship between the object of study and itself, the determination of the author's feelings and thoughts, the analysis of one's performance interpretation and the interpretation of another performer, etc.;

- a cognitive humanitarian object causes different feelings, interpretations, relationships both in the group and from each student, which creates an inexhaustible state of the created and created artistic image;

- the development of the value attitude to the artistic work is based on the students' own artistic, musical and life experience, its dependence, author, performer, style, style, genre, era, interpretation;

- the essence of knowing the humanities is in the reflective nature, in the development of individual meanings Improving the professional qualification of music listeners of undergraduate students of music education is more effective in the conditions of creative self-awareness of the student. Philosophical, sociological and psychological levels are distinguished in the analysis of scientific literature on the problem of self-realization of a person. At the philosophical level, the essence of a person, his main forces, the essence of the process of self-realization and its forms, the role of cultural values in the process of self-realization, which determine the specific characteristics of the mentality of a certain nation, Cultural and historical types of self-awareness are reflected [5].

In the process of mastering the musical pedagogical components of the students, questions about the ways and means of self-realization of the individual in certain socio-cultural conditions are solved. At the level of pedagogical competence, personal qualities and external conditions are analyzed, people are encouraged to express themselves effectively, motivational bases of self-awareness are studied.

Music pedagogy analysis of research and study of actual pedagogical practice shows that with a clear understanding of the need for scientific development of the concept of "self-awareness", "self-development", "improving the ability to listen to music", the understanding of the essence of this phenomenon is carried out in the context of studying concepts close to its importance: self-determination, self-organization, self-management, self- realization, self-

expression. Thus, the phenomenon of self-awareness appears as one of the functional blocks of a person's self-development. He studies the social functions of the future music teacher, his role in the process of socialization of young people, issues related to personality improvement, creativity, and self-awareness [7].

The interpretation of this concept is chosen depending on how the problem of self-awareness is included in the scope of the researcher's scientific interests. Self-awareness, self-expression, self-affirmation, independence, listening, listening comprehension, listening thinking, the ability to achieve one's goals, to protect one's rights in appropriate situations, self-awareness is expressed in a system of various relationships in which personality is included.

Self-awareness of students is the implementation of a system of relationships in the process of purposefully formed pedagogical guidance and educational influences that make up the content of creative self-awareness. Realization of these relations determines the essence of the phenomenon of creative self-realization.

Music education considers the creative self-awareness of undergraduate students as a symbol of their purposefully formed diverse relationships, creative abilities, personal self-expression to others in interactions with the world, people.

In the process of music pedagogy education, the improvement of students' listening ability takes place in the process of studying the educational subjects of the humanitarian cycle, their distinctive feature is "a special way of teaching to improve the experience of realizing emotional-volitional and emotional-value relations. is a complaint.

In accordance with the nature of the humanities, therefore, the subject itself cannot be assimilated only at the level of values, since its true assimilation involves the determination of meaning and relations through internal polemics, feelings, experience, and sub- objects means communication with the future music teacher, feeling oneself in the product of one's creativity. Research shows that the characteristics of the content of humanities determine the specific characteristics of the music teacher's knowledge in the process of professional personal formation. These are:

- effective knowledge of the humanitarian topic in the context of communication. It is a dialogue between the teacher and the student, the author of the musical work and the listener, the work of art itself and the translator. Dialogicity is manifested in the relationship between the object of study and itself, the determination of the author's feelings and thoughts, the analysis of one's performance interpretation and the interpretation of another performer, etc.;

- a cognitive humanitarian object causes different feelings, interpretations, relationships both in the group and from each student, which creates an inexhaustible state of the created and created artistic image;

- the development of the value attitude to the artistic work is based on the students' own artistic, musical and life experience, its dependence, author, performer, style, style, genre, era, interpretation;

- the essence of knowing the humanities is in the reflective nature, in the development of individual meanings

Conclusion Based on this point of view, the content of professional musical pedagogical education is not reduced to scientific knowledge, but to the emotional-volitional world of artistic, historical traditions and modern innovations, value orientations and relationships, personal

creative expressions and activity system, otherwise in other words, it includes different experiences.

In addition to the study of musical pedagogical education, it is aimed at developing the personal structure of the student's mind through musical culture. In other words, by developing a creative attitude to music culture (A. Barenboim), it is necessary to teach students creativity, and by teaching them to work creatively, we should emphasize their independence and the possibility of self-development.

REFERENCES

1. Abdullaeva Q. M. Maxsus fanlarni o'qitishda bo'lajak o'qituvchilarning kasbiy bilim va ko'nikmalarini shakllantirishning metodik asoslari: Dis: ped. fan nom. - Toshkent, 2006. B. 182.
2. Abdullin E. B. Metodologicheskiy analiz problem muzыkальnoy pedagogiki v sisteme vysshego obrazovaniya: Uchebnoe posobie. M. 1990.
3. Raximov B. X. Bo'lajak uqituvchilarda kasbiy-madaniy munosabatlarning shakllanishi: Diss. ped. fan. tnom. - Toshkent. 2002. B. 161
4. Xalilov F. N. Didakticheskie osnovы instrumental'no-ispolnitel'skiy podgotovki budущix uchiteley muzыki: Diss. d-ra ped. nauk. Toshkent. 2006. St. 266.
5. Yuldoshev U.Yu. Milliy maqom asarlari asosida bo'lajak musiqa o'qituvchisining ijodiy tafakkurini rivojlantirish. Ped.fan. falsafa dok. ... diss. – T. 2020. – 148 b.
6. Muslimov N.A. Kasb ta'limi o'qituvchisini kasbiy shakllantirishning nazariy-metodik asoslari: Ped. fan. dok. ... dis. avtoref. – T.:. 2007. – 47b.
7. Panjiyev Q.B. O'zbek xalq qo'shiqlari vositasida bo'lajak musiqa o'quvchilarini kasbiy tayyorgarligini takomillashtirish. Ped. fan. dok. .. diss. –T., 2022. - 248 b.